

Ruled Surface Pair Generated by Darboux Vectors of a Curve and Its Natural Lift in \mathbb{R}_1^3

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Abstract: In this study, firstly, the darboux vector \overline{W} of the natural lift $\overline{\alpha}$ of a curve α are calculated in terms of those of α in \mathbb{R}_1^3 . Secondly, we obtained striction lines and distribution parameters of ruled surface pair generated by by Darboux vectors of the curve α and its natural lift $\overline{\alpha}$. Finally, for α and $\overline{\alpha}$ those notions are compared with each other.

Key Words: Lift, ruled surface, striction line, distribution parameter.

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§1. Introduction and Preliminary Notes

The concepts of the natural lift curve and geodesic sprays have first been given by Thorpe in [17]. Thorpe proved the natural lift $\overline{\alpha}$ of the curve α is an integral curve of the geodesic spray iff α is an geodesic on M . Çalışkan at al. studied the natural lift curves of the spherical indicatrices of tangent, principal normal, binormal vectors and fixed centrode of a curve in [16]. They gave some interesting results about the original curve, depending on the assumption that the natural lift curve should be the integral curve of the geodesic spray on the tangent bundle $T(S^2)$. Some properties of \overline{M} -vector field Z defined on a hypersurface M of \overline{M} were studied by Agashe in [1]. \overline{M} -integral curve of Z and \overline{M} -geodesic spray are defined by Çalışkan and Sivridağ. They gave the main theorem: The natural lift $\overline{\alpha}$ of the curve α (in \overline{M}) is an \overline{M} -integral curve of the geodesic spray Z iff α is an \overline{M} -geodesic in [8]. Bilici et al. have proposed the natural lift curves and the geodesic sprays for the spherical indicatrices of the the involute evolute curve couple in Euclidean 3-space. They gave some interesting results about the evolute curve, depending on the assumption that the natural lift curve of the spherical indicatrices of the involute should be the integral curve on the tangent bundle $T(S^2)$ in [6]. Then Bilici applied this problem to involutes of a timelike curve in Minkowski 3-space (see [7]). Ergün and Çalışkan defined the concepts of the natural lift curve and geodesic spray in Minkowski 3-space in [10]. The analogue of the theorem of Thorpe was given in Minkowski 3-space by Ergün and Çalışkan in

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[10]. Çalışkan and Ergün defined \overline{M} -vector field Z , \overline{M} -geodesic spray, \overline{M} -integral curve of Z , \overline{M} -geodesic in [9]. The analogue of the theorem of Sivridağ and Çalışkan was given in Minkowski 3-space by Ergün and Çalışkan in [10]. Walrave characterized the curve with constant curvature in Minkowski 3-space in [16]. In differential geometry, especially the theory of space curve, the Darboux vector is the areal velocity vector of the Frenet frame of a spacere curve. It is named after Gaston Darboux who discovered it. In term of the Frenet-Serret apparatus, the darboux vector W can be expressed as $W = \tau T + \kappa B$, details are given in Lambert et al. in [13].

Let Minkowski 3-space \mathbb{R}_1^3 be the vector space \mathbb{R}^3 equipped with the Lorentzian inner product g given by

$$g(X, X) = -x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2$$

where $X = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3$. A vector $X = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is said to be timelike if $g(X, X) < 0$, spacelike if $g(X, X) > 0$ and lightlike (or null) if $g(X, X) = 0$. Similarly, an arbitrary curve $\alpha = \alpha(t)$ in \mathbb{R}_1^3 where t is a pseudo-arclength parameter, can locally be timelike, spacelike or null (lightlike), if all of its velocity vectors $\dot{\alpha}(t)$ are respectively timelike, spacelike or null (lightlike), for every $t \in I \subset \mathbb{R}$. A lightlike vector X is said to be positive (resp. negative) if and only if $x_1 > 0$ (resp. $x_1 < 0$) and a timelike vector X is said to be positive (resp. negative) if and only if $x_1 > 0$ (resp. $x_1 < 0$). The norm of a vector X is defined by [14]

$$\|X\|_{IL} = \sqrt{|g(X, X)|}.$$

We denote by $\{T(t), N(t), B(t)\}$ the moving Frenet frame along the curve α . Then T, N and B are the tangent, the principal normal and the binormal vector of the curve α , respectively.

Let α be a unit speed timelike space curve with curvature κ and torsion τ . Let Frenet vector fields of α be $\{T, N, B\}$. In this trihedron, T is timelike vector field, N and B are spacelike vector fields. For this vectors, we can write

$$T \times N = B, \quad N \times B = -T, \quad B \times T = N,$$

where \times is the Lorentzian cross product, [4]. in space \mathbb{R}_1^3 . Then, Frenet formulas are given by

$$T' = \kappa N, N' = \kappa T + \tau B, B' = -\tau N, [16].$$

The Frenet instantaneous rotation vector for the timelike curve is given by $W = \tau T + \kappa B$.

Let α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal. In this trihedron, we assume that T and B are spacelike vector fields and N is a timelike vector field. In this situation,

$$T \times N = B, \quad N \times B = T, \quad B \times T = -N,$$

Then, Frenet formulas are given by

$$T' = \kappa N, N' = \kappa T + \tau B, B' = \tau N, [16].$$

The Frenet instantaneous rotation vector for the spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal is given by $W = \tau T - \kappa B$.

Let α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal. In this trihedron, we assume that T and N are spacelike vector fields and B is a timelike vector field. In this situation,

$$T \times N = -B, \quad N \times B = T, \quad B \times T = N,$$

Then, Frenet formulas are given by,

$$T' = \kappa N, \quad N' = -\kappa T + \tau B, \quad B' = \tau N, \quad [16].$$

The Frenet instantaneous rotation vector for the spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal is given by $W = -\tau T + \kappa B$.

Lemma 1.1([15]) *Let X and Y be nonzero Lorentz orthogonal vectors in \mathbb{R}_1^3 . If X is timelike, then Y is spacelike.*

Lemma 1.2([15]) *Let X and Y be positive (negative) timelike vectors in \mathbb{R}_1^3 . Then*

$$g(X, Y) \leq \|X\| \|Y\|$$

with equality if and only if X and Y are linearly dependent.

Lemma 1.3([15]) (1) *Let X and Y be positive (negative) timelike vectors in \mathbb{R}_1^3 . By the Lemma 2, there is unique nonnegative real number $\varphi(X, Y)$ such that*

$$g(X, Y) = \|X\| \|Y\| \cosh \varphi(X, Y),$$

the Lorentzian timelike angle between X and Y is defined to be $\varphi(X, Y)$.

(2) *Let X and Y be spacelike vectors in \mathbb{R}_1^3 that span a spacelike vector subspace. Then we have*

$$|g(X, Y)| \leq \|X\| \|Y\|.$$

Hence, there is a unique real number $\varphi(X, Y)$ between 0 and π such that

$$g(X, Y) = \|X\| \|Y\| \cos \varphi(X, Y),$$

the Lorentzian spacelike angle between X and Y is defined to be $\varphi(X, Y)$.

(3) *Let X and Y be spacelike vectors in \mathbb{R}_1^3 that span a timelike vector subspace. Then we have*

$$g(X, Y) > \|X\| \|Y\|.$$

Hence, there is a unique positive real number $\varphi(X, Y)$ between 0 and π such that

$$|g(X, Y)| = \|X\| \|Y\| \cosh \varphi(X, Y),$$

the Lorentzian timelike angle between X and Y is defined to be $\varphi(X, Y)$.

(4) *Let X be a spacelike vector and Y be a positive timelike vector in \mathbb{R}_1^3 . Then there is*

a unique nonnegative reel number $\varphi(X, Y)$ such that

$$|g(X, Y)| = \|X\| \|Y\| \sinh \varphi(X, Y),$$

the Lorentzian timelike angle between X and Y is defined to be $\varphi(X, Y)$.

For the curve α with a timelike tangent, let θ be a Lorentzian timelike angle between the spacelike binormal unit $-B$ and the Frenet instantaneous rotation vector W .

a) If $|\kappa| > |\tau|$, then W is a spacelike vector. In this situation, from Lemma 3 (3) we can write

$$\kappa = \|W\| \cosh \theta, \quad \tau = \|W\| \sinh \theta$$

$\|W\|^2 = g(W, W) = \kappa^2 - \tau^2$ and $C = \frac{W}{\|W\|} = \sinh \theta T + \cosh \theta B$, where C is unit vector of direction W .

b) If $|\kappa| < |\tau|$, then W is a timelike vector. In this situation, from Lemma 3 (4) we can write

$$\kappa = \|W\| \sinh \theta, \quad \tau = \|W\| \cosh \theta$$

$\|W\|^2 = -g(W, W) = -(\kappa^2 - \tau^2)$ and $C = \cosh \theta T + \sinh \theta B$.

For the curve α with a timelike principal normal, let θ be an angle between the B and the W , if B and W spacelike vectors that span a spacelike vector subspace then by the Lemma 3 (2) we can write

$$\kappa = \|W\| \cos \theta, \quad \tau = \|W\| \sin \theta$$

$\|W\|^2 = g(W, W) = \kappa^2 + \tau^2$ and $C = \sin \theta T - \cos \theta B$.

For the curve α with a timelike binormal, let θ be a Lorentzian timelike angle between the $-B$ and the W .

a) If $|\kappa| < |\tau|$, then W is a spacelike vector. In this situation, from Lemma 3 (4) we can write

$$\kappa = \|W\| \sinh \theta, \quad \tau = \|W\| \cosh \theta$$

$\|W\|^2 = g(W, W) = \tau^2 - \kappa^2$ and $C = -\cosh \theta T + \sinh \theta B$.

(b) If $|\kappa| > |\tau|$, then W is a timelike vector. In this situation, from Lemma 3 (1) we have

$$\kappa = \|W\| \cosh \theta, \quad \tau = \|W\| \sinh \theta$$

$\|W\|^2 = -g(W, W) = -(\tau^2 - \kappa^2)$ and $C = -\sinh \theta T + \cosh \theta B$.

From [10], we know that if α be a unit speed timelike space curve, then the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of α is a spacelike space curve; if α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal, then the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of α is a timelike space curve; if α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal, then the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of α is a spacelike space curve. If α be a unit speed timelike space curve and $\bar{\alpha}$ be the natural lift of α , then from [12] we know

that

$$\bar{T}(s) = N(s), \quad \bar{N}(s) = -\frac{\kappa(s)}{\|W\|}T(s) - \frac{\tau(s)}{\|W\|}B(s), \quad \bar{B}(s) = -\frac{\tau(s)}{\|W\|}T(s) - \frac{\kappa(s)}{\|W\|}B(s),$$

and if α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal and $\bar{\alpha}$ be the natural lift of α , then

$$\bar{T}(s) = N(s), \quad \bar{N}(s) = \frac{\kappa(s)}{\|W\|}T(s) + \frac{\tau(s)}{\|W\|}B(s), \quad \bar{B}(s) = \frac{\tau(s)}{\|W\|}T(s) - \frac{\kappa(s)}{\|W\|}B(s),$$

and if α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal and $\bar{\alpha}$ be the natural lift of α , then

$$\bar{T}(s) = N(s), \quad \bar{N}(s) = -\frac{\kappa(s)}{\|W\|}T(s) - \frac{\tau(s)}{\|W\|}B(s), \quad \bar{B}(s) = \frac{\tau(s)}{\|W\|}T(s) + \frac{\kappa(s)}{\|W\|}B(s).$$

Definition 1.1([4]) *Let M be a hypersurface in \mathbb{R}_1^3 and let $\alpha : I \rightarrow M$ be a parametrized curve. α is called an integral curve of X if*

$$\frac{d}{ds}(\alpha(s)) = X(\alpha(s)) \quad (\text{for all } s \in I),$$

where X is a smooth tangent vector field on M . We have

$$TM = \bigcup_{P \in M} T_P M = \chi(M),$$

where $T_P M$ is the tangent space of M at P and $\chi(M)$ is the space of vector fields on M .

Definition 1.2([5]) *A parameterized curve $\alpha : I \rightarrow M$, $\bar{\alpha} : I \rightarrow TM$ given by*

$$\bar{\alpha}(s) = (\alpha(s), \alpha'(s)) = \alpha'(s)|_{\alpha(s)}$$

is called the natural lift of α on TM . Thus, we can write

$$\frac{d\bar{\alpha}}{ds} = \frac{d}{ds}(\alpha'(s)|_{\alpha(s)}) = D_{\alpha'(s)}\alpha'(s)$$

where D is the Levi-Civita connection on \mathbb{R}_1^3 .

A ruled surface is generated by a one-parameter family of straight lines and it possesses a parametric representation

$$X(s, v) = \alpha(s) + ve(s),$$

where $\alpha(s)$ represents a space curve which is called the base curve and e is a unit vector representing the direction of a straight line.

The striction point on a ruled surface X is the foot of the common normal between two consecutive generators (or ruling). The set of striction points defines the striction curve given

as

$$\beta(s) = \alpha(s) - \frac{g(\alpha', e')}{g(e', e')} e(s) \quad [2].$$

The distribution parameter of the ruled surface X is defined by ([2])

$$P_e = \frac{\det(\alpha', e, e')}{\|e'\|^2}$$

and the ruled surface is developable if and only if $P_e = 0$.

§2. Ruled Surface Pair Generated by Darboux Vectors of a Curve and Its Natural Lift in \mathbb{R}_1^3

In this section the darbox vector \bar{W} of the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of a curve α are calculated in terms of those of α in \mathbb{R}_1^3 . We obtained striction lines and distribution parameters of ruled surface pair generated by Darboux vectors of the curve α and its natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$. Let α be a unit speed timelike space curve. Then the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of α is a spacelike space curve.

Proposition 2.1 *Let α be a unit speed timelike space curve and the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of the curve α be a space curve with curvature $\bar{\kappa}$ and torsion $\bar{\tau}$. Then*

$$\bar{\kappa}(s) = \frac{\|W\|}{\kappa(s)}, \bar{\tau}(s) = -\frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2}.$$

Proposition 2.2 *Let α be a unit speed timelike space curve and the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of the curve α be a space curve.*

(i) *If the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ is a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal, then*

$$\bar{W} = \frac{\bar{\tau}(s)}{\kappa(s)}T - \left(\frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2} \right) N + B$$

(ii) *If the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ is a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal, then*

$$\bar{W} = \frac{\tau(s)}{\kappa(s)}T + \left(\frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2} \right) N + B$$

Let X and \bar{X} be two ruled surfaces which is given by

$$X(s, v) = \alpha(s) + vC(s), \quad \bar{X}(s, v) = \bar{\alpha}(s) + v\bar{C}(s)$$

The striction curves of X and \bar{X} are given by $\beta(s) = \alpha(s) - \lambda C(s)$ and $\bar{\beta}(s) = \bar{\alpha}(s) -$

$\mu \bar{C}(s)$, respectively. The distribution parameters of the ruled surfaces X and \bar{X} are defined by

$$P_C = \frac{\det(\alpha', C, C')}{\|C'\|^2} \text{ and } \bar{P}_{\bar{C}} = \frac{\det(\bar{\alpha}', \bar{C}, \bar{C}')}{\|\bar{C}'\|^2}.$$

Proposition 2.3 *If the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ is a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= \frac{\tau'(s)}{[\kappa'(s)]^2 - [\tau'(s)]^2} \|W\|, \\ \mu &= -\frac{\|\bar{W}\| \kappa(s) \sigma'(s)}{-\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} + \kappa(s)\sigma(s)\right]^2 + [\sigma'(s)]^2 + [\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2}, \\ P_C = 0, \bar{P}_{\bar{C}} &= \frac{\sigma(s)\tau(s)^2 - \kappa(s)\left(\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} + \kappa(s)\sigma(s)\right)}{\left|-\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} + \kappa(s)\sigma(s)\right]^2 + [\sigma'(s)]^2 + [\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2\right|} \end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma(s) = \frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2}$.

Proposition 2.4 *If the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ is a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= \frac{\tau'(s)}{[\kappa'(s)]^2 - [\tau'(s)]^2} \|W\|, \\ \mu &= \frac{\|\bar{W}\| \kappa(s) \sigma'(s)}{-\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} - \kappa(s)\sigma(s)\right]^2 + [-\sigma'(s)]^2 + [-\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2}, \\ P_C = 0, \bar{P}_{\bar{C}} &= \frac{-\sigma(s)\tau(s)^2 - \kappa(s)\left(\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} - \kappa(s)\sigma(s)\right)}{\left|-\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} - \kappa(s)\sigma(s)\right]^2 + [-\sigma'(s)]^2 + [-\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2\right|} \end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma(s) = \frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2}$.

Let α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal. Then the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of α is a timelike space curve.

Proposition 2.5 *Let α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal and the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of the curve α be a space curve with curvature $\bar{\kappa}$ and torsion $\bar{\tau}$. Then*

$$\bar{\kappa}(s) = \frac{\|\bar{W}\|}{\kappa(s)}, \bar{\tau}(s) = \frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2}.$$

Proposition 2.6 *Let α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal and the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of the curve α be a space curve, then*

$$\bar{W} = \frac{\tau(s)}{\kappa(s)}T + \left(\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2} \right)N + B.$$

Let X and \bar{X} be two ruled surfaces which is given by

$$X(s, v) = \alpha(s) + vC(s), \quad \bar{X}(s, v) = \bar{\alpha}(s) + v\bar{C}(s)$$

Proposition 2.7 *The striction curves of X and \bar{X} are given by $\beta(s) = \alpha(s) - \lambda C(s)$ and $\bar{\beta}(s) = \bar{\alpha}(s) - \mu\bar{C}(s)$, respectively. The distribution parameters of the ruled surfaces X and \bar{X} are defined by $P_C = \frac{\det(\alpha', C, C')}{\|C'\|^2}$ and $\bar{P}_{\bar{C}} = \frac{\det(\bar{\alpha}', \bar{C}, \bar{C}')}{\|\bar{C}'\|^2}$. Then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= -\frac{\tau'(s)}{[\kappa'(s)]^2 + [\tau'(s)]^2} \|W\|, \\ \mu &= -\frac{(2\tau(s) + \sigma'(s))\kappa(s)\|\bar{W}\|}{\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} \right]^2 - [2\tau(s) + \sigma'(s)]^2 + [\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2}, \\ P_C &= 0, \quad \bar{P}_{\bar{C}} = \frac{-\kappa(s)\left(\frac{\kappa(s)\tau'(s) - \kappa'(s)\tau(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} + \kappa(s)\sigma(s) \right) + \sigma(s)\tau(s)^2}{\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} + \kappa(s)\sigma(s) \right]^2 - [2\tau(s) + \sigma'(s)]^2 + [\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2} \end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma(s) = \frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2}$.

Let α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal. Then the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of α is a spacelike space curve.

Proposition 2.8 *Let α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal and the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of the curve α be a space curve with curvature $\bar{\kappa}$ and torsion $\bar{\tau}$. Then*

$$\bar{\kappa}(s) = \frac{\|W\|}{\kappa(s)}, \quad \bar{\tau}(s) = \frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) - \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2}.$$

Proposition 2.9 *Let α be a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal and the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ of the curve α be a space curve.*

(i) *If the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ is a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal, then*

$$\bar{W} = -\frac{\tau(s)}{\kappa(s)}T + \left(\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) - \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2} \right)N - B.$$

(ii) If the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ is a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal, then

$$\bar{W} = \frac{\tau(s)}{\kappa(s)}T + \left(\frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2} \right)N + B.$$

Let X and \bar{X} be two ruled surfaces which is given by

$$X(s, v) = \alpha(s) + vC(s), \quad \bar{X}(s, v) = \bar{\alpha}(s) + v\bar{C}(s)$$

The striction curves of X and \bar{X} are given by $\beta(s) = \alpha(s) - \lambda C(s)$ and $\bar{\beta}(s) = \bar{\alpha}(s) - \mu\bar{C}(s)$, respectively. The distribution parameters of the ruled surfaces X and \bar{X} are defined by

$$P_C = \frac{\det(\alpha', C, C')}{\|C'\|^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{P}_{\bar{C}} = \frac{\det(\bar{\alpha}', \bar{C}, \bar{C}')}{\|\bar{C}'\|^2}.$$

Proposition 2.10 *If the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ is a unit speed spacelike space curve with a timelike binormal, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= -\frac{\tau'(s)}{[\tau'(s)]^2 - [\kappa'(s)]^2} \|W\|, \\ \mu &= -\frac{(2\tau(s) + \sigma'(s))\kappa(s)\|\bar{W}\|}{\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} \right]^2 + [2\tau(s) + \sigma'(s)]^2 - [\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2}, \\ P_C &= 0, \quad \bar{P}_{\bar{C}} = \frac{\kappa(s) \left(\frac{\kappa(s)\tau'(s) - \kappa'(s)\tau(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} - \kappa(s)\sigma(s) \right) + \sigma(s)\tau(s)^2}{\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} - \kappa(s)\sigma(s) \right]^2 + [2\tau(s) + \sigma'(s)]^2 - [\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2} \end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma(s) = \frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2}$.

Proposition 2.11 *If the natural lift $\bar{\alpha}$ is a unit speed spacelike space curve with a spacelike binormal, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= -\frac{\tau'(s)}{[\tau'(s)]^2 - [\kappa'(s)]^2} \|W\|, \\ \mu &= -\frac{(-2\tau(s) + \sigma'(s))\kappa(s)\|\bar{W}\|}{\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} \right]^2 + [-2\tau(s) + \sigma'(s)]^2 - [\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2}, \\ P_C &= 0, \quad \bar{P}_{\bar{C}} = \frac{\kappa(s) \left(-\frac{\kappa(s)\tau'(s) - \kappa'(s)\tau(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} + \kappa(s)\sigma(s) \right) - \sigma(s)\tau(s)^2}{\left[\frac{-\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)^2} + \kappa(s)\sigma(s) \right]^2 + [-2\tau(s) - \sigma'(s)]^2 - [-\sigma(s)\tau(s)]^2} \end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma(s) = \frac{\kappa'(s)\tau(s) + \kappa(s)\tau'(s)}{\kappa(s)\|W\|^2}$.

Example 2.1 Let $\alpha(s) = \left(\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3}s, \frac{1}{3}\cos(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{1}{3}\sin(\sqrt{3}s)\right)$ be a unit speed (timelike curve) timelike circular helix with

$$T(s) = \left(\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3}, -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\sin(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\cos(\sqrt{3}s)\right),$$

$$N(s) = \left(0, -\cos(\sqrt{3}s), -\sin(\sqrt{3}s)\right),$$

$$B(s) = \left(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}, \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3}\sin(\sqrt{3}s), -\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3}\cos(\sqrt{3}s)\right) \text{ and } \kappa = 1, \tau = 2,$$

$$C(s) = (1, 0, 0).$$

$$X(s, t) = \left(\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3}s + t, \frac{1}{3}\cos(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{1}{3}\sin(\sqrt{3}s)\right)$$

and

$$\bar{X}(s, t) = \left(\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} + \frac{2t}{\sqrt{3}}, -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\sin(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\cos(\sqrt{3}s) + \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}}\right).$$

Figure 1

Example 2.2 Let $\alpha(s) = \left(\cosh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}, \sinh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right)$ be a unit speed spacelike hyperbolic helix with

$$T(s) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sinh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\cosh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right)$$

$$N(s) = \left(\cosh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right), 0, \sinh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right),$$

$$B(s) = \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cosh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \right), \text{ and } \kappa = \frac{1}{2}, \tau = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$C(s) = \left(\sinh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right), 0, \cosh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \right),$$

$$X(s, t) = \left(\cosh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + t \sinh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}, \sinh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + t \cosh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \right)$$

and

$$\bar{X}(s, t) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{2}}t, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cosh\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \right)$$

Figure 2

Example 2.3 Let $\alpha(s) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}s, \frac{2}{3} \cos(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{2}{3} \sin(\sqrt{3}s) \right)$ be a unit speed (spacelike curve with timelike binormal) spacelike circular helix with

$$T(s) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}, -\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} \sin(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} \cos(\sqrt{3}s) \right),$$

$$N(s) = \left(0, -\cos(\sqrt{3}s), -\sin(\sqrt{3}s) \right),$$

$$B(s) = \left(\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3}, -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} \sin(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} \cos(\sqrt{3}s) \right) \text{ and } \kappa = 2, \tau = 1$$

$$C(s) = (1, 0, 0)$$

$$X(s, t) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}s + t, -\frac{2}{3} \cos(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{2}{3} \sin(\sqrt{3}s) \right)$$

and

$$\bar{X}(s, t) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}s - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}t, -\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} \sin(\sqrt{3}s), \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} \cos(\sqrt{3}s) - \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}t \right)$$

Figure 3

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